

Research

Relationship between Monopoles and Quantum Entanglemen

by: Dixon Steven Gordillo Giraldo
Contact: dixonsteven721@gmail.com

11/06/2025

Index:

1. Introduction
2. Monopoles
3. Quantum Entanglement
4. Hypothesis
5. Symmetric Physics
6. Dirac String
7. Comparison
8. Graph and Equation
9. Experimentation
10. Conclusion

Introducción:

In physics, it is well known that magnetism manifests itself in the form of dipoles: every magnet has a north and a south pole. However, over the years a question has arisen: is it possible for magnetic monopoles to exist?

This article proposes a hypothesis that addresses this question from a symmetric quantum perspective, suggesting that monopoles would not exist in isolation but rather as quantum-entangled complementary pairs.

But first a brief explanation of these two terms.

Magnetic Monopoles:

In conventional magnetism, we always find pairs of poles: north and south. But if we cut a magnet in half, we don't get a single pole, but two smaller magnets, each with its own poles

Some theoretical models predict the possible existence of magnetic monopoles—particles that carry only one magnetic pole. These monopoles would be analogous to positive or negative electric charges but in the context of the magnetic field.

Quantum Entanglement:

Quantum entanglement is a phenomenon in which two or more particles become connected so that the state of one instantaneously affects the state of the other, regardless of the distance between them. This connection is neither physical nor visible, but it is real and has been experimentally confirmed.

Hypothesis:

Magnetic monopoles could exist as quantum-entangled pairs, where each manifests north or south pole properties at different points in space but remains connected through entanglement, this could explain their apparent absence in direct observations and their unconventional behavior in certain physical systems

This hypothesis proposes that magnetic monopoles do not exist in isolation but always appear in pairs connected through quantum entanglement, maintaining a fundamental symmetry between their opposite properties.

This quantum connection does not depend on distance or classical interaction but reflects a profound symmetry of the magnetic field, where the presence of one monopole necessarily implies the existence of the other, ensuring conservation of the system's total magnetic charge

So, entanglement acts as a natural symmetry mechanism, ensuring that monopoles behave as quantum reflections of each other, even across space-time.

Dirac String:

In some theoretical developments, such as those of Paul Dirac in 1931, it was proposed that the existence of magnetic monopoles would imply the quantization of electric charge. However, this formulation relied on a construct known as the “Dirac string,” an unobservable mathematical singularity that maintains magnetic field consistency around the monopole, although not from a fully relativistic perspective.

In contrast, this hypothesis proposes a relativistic and symmetric model, where monopoles always exist in quantum-entangled pairs, avoiding the need for a string or singularity and proposing a more direct physical connection between the existence of the monopole and the principle of quantum symmetry.

Below is a comparative framework between both theories:

Aspect:	Cuerda de Dirac	Hipótesis de Monopolos Entrelazados Cuánticamente
Theoretical Origin	Proposed by Paul Dirac in 1931 to justify the existence of magnetic monopoles.	My proposal based on quantum entanglement.
Nature of the Connection	Invisible (mathematical) connection between the monopole and a region of space through a singular string.	Real physical connection based on quantum entanglement between separated monopoles.
Type of Connection	Mathematical singularity, not directly observable.	Non-local quantum correlation, indirectly measurable through effects on the entangled system.
Number of Monopoles	There may be only one, connected to a unidirectional string.	There are always at least two monopoles quantumly bound together (as correlated pairs).
Observable Manifestation	The string must be undetectable to preserve gauge symmetry.	There are always at least two monopoles quantumly bound together (as correlated pairs).
Modern Interpretation	Interpreted as a useful but non-physical mathematical construct.	Interpreted as a physical and real connection based on currently studied quantum phenomena.

Equation and Graph:

Graph

The proposed equation describes a system of two magnetic monopoles—one positive and one negative—that are quantum-entangled that means that their states are connected regardless of distance between their

This connection is represented by a symmetrical state that does not allow us to distinguish which one is in which state individually: knowledge of one implies knowledge of the other.

$$|\Psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_+\rangle|\psi_-\rangle + |\psi_-\rangle|\psi_+\rangle)$$

(The equation presents two possible intertwined configurations. The sum represents the impossibility of distinguishing which is which, maintaining perfect symmetry between them)

Experimentation:

My proposal for experimentation and verification of this theory is to carry out tests with methods already used previously for the detection of these monopoles, but seeking to detect a quantum link signature between at least two of them using one of the following methods

- MoEDAL (LHC – CERN): Specifically designed to search for magnetic monopoles.
- Bose-Einstein condensates: Field configurations have been created that simulate the existence of artificial monopoles
- Frustrated spin crystals (spin ice): In these materials, monopolar "quasiparticles" have been observed, especially under low temperature conditions.

A viable way to explore this hypothesis would be through spin-ice materials, in which the appearance of magnetic quasimonopoles has already been experimentally observed. It is proposed to isolate two regions where monopoles of opposite polarity emerge and study their behavior under controlled conditions. If quantum correlations are detected that cannot be explained by classical interactions, this could be interpreted as indirect evidence of quantum entanglement between the monopoles. This approach would not only take advantage of existing experimental techniques but would also allow the investigation of a phenomenon that has not yet been explored in this context.

Conclusion:

Although fundamental monopoles have not yet been detected in nature, the study of monopolar quasiparticles in physical systems such as spin ice opens an experimental window to explore this idea. If any type of entanglement between these entities were confirmed, it would establish an unprecedented precedent that could reshape our understanding of nonlocality, the structure of the quantum vacuum, and the fundamental symmetries of nature.